

Join of 4Q1 (4QGen-Exod^a) frags. 9 and 47

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James R. Davila (1994) published as the manuscript 4Q1 or 4QGen-Exod^a an assemblage of fragments, preserving parts of Genesis 22 through Exodus 8 and written in the same hand, which earlier editors had brought together. In addition, he published twenty-three tiny unidentified fragments (4Q1 frags. 38-61) which had previously been assigned to or associated with 4Q1 on the basis of physical and palaeographic features. One of those unidentified fragments (4Q1 frag. 60) has been reassigned to 4Q49 (Tigchelaar, 2021). I am not aware of other identifications of 4Q1 frags. 38-61.

The unidentified fragment 4Q1 frag. 47 joins materially and textually to 4Q1 frag. 9 at the left side of lines 12-13. These lines may now be transcribed as follows (frag. 47 in red)

[שר בית הסהר] ביד יוסף את כל האסירם אשר בבית הסהר ו[את כל אשר עשים שם]	12
[הוא היה עשה א]ין שר בית הסהר ראה את כל מאומה[] ביד[ו באשר יהוה אתו]	13

4Q1 frag. 9 (bottom) + frag. 47 joined with Gimp; images taken from
<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-284249>
<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-284246>

James R. Davila (1994) "1. 4QGen-Exod^a," in *Qumran Cave 4 VII: Genesis to Numbers*, ed. Eugene Ulrich and Frank Moore Cross; Discoveries in the Judaean Desert XII (Oxford: Clarendon Press)
Eibert Tigchelaar (2021) "4Q1 (4QGen-Exod^a) Frag. 60 + 4Q49 (4QJudg^a)."
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5114482>